

DAMAGE PROPAGATION IN CFRP STIFFENED STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Experimental results of impact damaged CFRP stiffened panel elements are presented. The influence of the impact energy in the range of barely visible impact damage (BVID) on the onset of delamination growth under cyclic compression loading is described. The damage development was monitored with help of NDI techniques like US in-situ and acoustic emission measurements. The experimental results show that depending on the impact energy the local delamination growth onset under compressive fatigue loading is different.

INTRODUCTION

The investigation of the capability of fibre-reinforced materials to tolerate reasonable level of damage or defects that may be encountered during manufacture or in service is a very important topic that can influence the criteria for predicting the performance of a composite structural part. Even with impacts that show little indication of damage at the surface, the matrix and fibre damage in the interior of the laminate can be significant. Delamination, matrix cracking and fibre breakage are the principal damage modes that may be present in composite structures. Delamination is of primary concern, because it may reduce the strength and stiffness of the material significantly and consequently the load bearing capability of the structure. An ongoing programme in the GARTEUR Group entitled "Damage Propagation in Composite Structural Elements" [1] has the aim to improve the modelling and prediction of composite structural performance in the presence of impact damage or manufacturing defects. The Institute is involved in the investigation to improve the understanding of delamination growth onset by careful experimentation including NDE-techniques.

In the present paper some phenomenological aspects of the delamination growth onset of barely visible impact damaged (BVID) blade stiffened CFRP panels are presented.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The CFRP material used to fabricate the blade stiffened structural elements was AS4/8552 (Hercules) unidirectional tape prepreg. The lay-up of the panels was $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$. The skin/stringer panels were co-cured with the one shot method developed in the Institute [2]. The specimens 120 mm by 85 mm, 3 mm thick with 20 mm blade stiffeners 41 mm apart, were cut

from big panels using a diamond saw. The loading surfaces were ground flat and parallel to assure an uniform axial compressive load introduction.

The BVID was introduced in an instrumented drop weight facility with following parameters: hemispherical steel impactor with a diameter of 10 mm, a mass of 0,390 kg and a drop height between 0.5 m and 1.5 m. The impactor energies were between 1.95 J and 5.74 J. The impact was localized at the panel faces on the opposite side to the junction between panel and stringer. The fatigue tests were performed on a Schenck servo-controlled hydraulic test machine, load controlled with sinusoidal axial loading at a frequency of 5 Hz. The specimens were simple supported at the loaded ends, the lateral edges were unsupported, see Fig. 1. An extensometer from Schenck with a gauge length of 10 mm was used to measure the strain at the specimens. All tests were done at room temperature.

During fatigue loading the ultrasonic-in situ method (USIS) [3] was used to evaluate the degree of damage progression. USIS allows the US inspection of specimens without removing them from the loading frame and the immersion of the specimens in a water tank. This can lead to misinterpretation of US measurements due to the water infiltration in debonded areas, especially at the rear face of impacted specimens. The ultrasonic equipment used was a Krautkrämer KB6000, a selfmade scanning mechanism and a PC for data management. The results of the US pulse-echo measurements are presented as a picture which shows areas of equal rear-wall echo amplitude, giving the possibility to visualize the damage development in the specimen easily.

Acoustic Emission (AE) was monitored during some of the fatigue tests. The piezo-electric transducer was positioned in the bay of the panels, near the impact damage, using a silicon gel as acoustic couplant. The equipment used was from Physical Acoustics (PAC 3400) and the transducer had resonant frequency of 150 kHz and a 40 dB preamplifier. The time signal from the testing machine was simultaneous recorded with the AE signal in order to correlate AE and load cycles.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Panels were impact damaged at the geometric centre of the bay, between the stringers. With the impact damage at this location it is easier to follow its development. An impact damage over the location of the stringers, could induce a damage into the stringers [4].

Fig. 2 shows the initial impact damaged area calculated from the US C-scans for different impact energies. The tendency is similar to the well known shape -a gradually increase of the damaged area with increasing impactor energies- after a maximum, perforation of the damaged area takes place. In the investigated panels no visible damage was found in the front face nor in the rear face of the skin.

The impacted panels were tested under compressive fatigue loading ($R = 10$) and US inspected after different number of load cycles to find the onset of delamination growth. Generally, multidirectional composites under compressive fatigue loading show degradation in stiffness even without impact damage. Significant changes in the load-strain curves for the panel with the lowest impact damage energy of 1.95 J were visible after about $2 \cdot 10^5$ load cycles at a level of 100 kN, as can be seen in Fig. 3. The damaged area increase was at this stage less than 10% compared to the initial impacted area. This means that the change in the slope of the measured curves can be attributed mainly to the degradation of the material.

Acoustic emission measurements help to understand the damage development in CFRP. In the investigated panels with noticeable delamination growth surfaces it was observed that there are periods of moderate AE activity and others with very high AE activity, as shown in Fig. 4. Panel PA 4 was impacted with 4.2 J and compressive fatigue loaded at a strain level of $\epsilon = 3800 \mu\text{m/m}$. Filtering out the most significant AE events, there was a period of high AE activity between 79000 and 83000 load cycles followed by a period of less activity until 88000 load cycles where again a higher AE activity was observed.

Through US- inspection it could be proved that there was a pronounced damaged area

growth during this period of loading as can be seen in Fig. 5. The damaged area grew in this period from about 3 % up to 8 % of the initial damaged area. The second curve in the figure shows the development of the damaged area for specimen PA 3, which was impacted with 5.74 J. A significant growth rate of the damaged area was observed in this panel in the first 5000 load cycles, although the fatigue loading strain was the same as in the case before.

A compilation of damaged area development, AE- counts and changes in the US- mean values, that is the mean value of all measured rear-wall amplitudes of the US signal, is presented in Fig. 6. As an example a US-picture of PA 3, at test begin and after 20000 load cycles is shown in Fig. 7. Changes in the grey scale mean changes in the measured rear-wall echo amplitude, i.e., white color: no degradation, black color: delamination. In the US picture after fatigue loading there is a delamination area in the - 45° fibre direction initiated from the impact damaged area followed by a degradation -not yet delaminated- in the + 45° and 0° direction. An US inspection after further loading would show a delaminated area over the whole region. So far a propagation of the delamination towards the stringer was not observed. This means that the delamination was stopped at the folding edge of the - 45° layer and tries to continue in the adjacent 45° layer. It seems that some nuclei of degraded material are necessary before a delamination propagates. A jumping of the delamination from ply to ply was also observed in other investigations [5, 6, 7]. There seems to exist a difference considering the starting of the delamination growth between an impact damage site and artificial inserts under loading. Nevertheless, a quantification of impact damage is required if the state of damage is to be accurately described especially for analytical simulation models.

A problem still to be solved with impact damage in composites is the scaling of results from laboratory specimens to small structural elements and finally to large structures [8]. Considerations of scale effects involve not only the geometrical ones but also the knowledge of failure mechanisms characteristic of flat specimens and structural elements, respectively. The degradation of laminates is one aspect which can influence the failure mechanism. Changes of the stiffness in a specimen can easily be measured with strain gauges, but not in bigger structures. A possible way to evaluate the degradation of the material in a small structural element is given by US inspection. As shown in Fig. 8, a quantification of the US rear-wall echo amplitude as a kind of distribution curve over the grey scale levels and the number of measured area points (every 2 mm scanning), is possible. Here the behaviour of two panels, e.g., PA1 and PA3 are compared. The curves represent the first US inspection before fatigue loading and the last measured one, respectively. A degradation of the PA1 laminate is visible since the maximum of the curve moves from 90 % towards 75 % without larger changes in the region >40 %. For PA3, where degradation was mainly near the impact damage, the distribution curve's maximum moves less towards smaller values, whereas the number of area points between 10% and 70% increases.

CONCLUSIONS

Experimental results of CFRP stiffened structural elements with BVID were presented. It could be shown that the onset of delamination growth under cyclic compression loading depends mainly on the impactor energy.

AE measurements showed that the damage development near the impact site is not a steady process but intermittent. There are periods of less acoustic activity followed by periods of high activity. It was possible to correlate AE measurement and US inspection. The US-in situ method showed that there are degradation nuclei before delamination grows.

Quantification of the US rear-wall echo amplitude allows us to differentiate between the general degradation of the laminate and the damage development due to impact damage.

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Figure 1. Compression fatigue test set-up

PA (AS4/8552)

Figure 2. Impact damaged area calculated from US-measurements

Figure 3. Load strain curves for PA1 after different load cycles

Figure 4. Intermittent acoustic emission counts over load cycles (PA4)

Figure 5. Damaged area development over load cycles (PA 3 and PA 4)

Figure 6. Damage development in PA 3

Figure 7. US-in situ pictures of PA3 at beginning and after 20000 load cycles

Figure 8. Quantification of US rear-wall echo amplitude